

AS PART OF THE CLEARING HOUSE
PROJECT.....

CLEARINGHOUSE
中欧城市森林应对方案

CO-DESIGN WORKSHOP

PROGRAM

SEPTEMBER 8 | 9H
AUDITORIUM X

FOR MORE INFORMATION...